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Idiopathic respiratory distress syndrome

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Abstract

Background: Idiopathic respiratory distress syndrome (IRDS) occurs in 13% of all births

Aim of the study: To determine the incidence, sex distribution, associated risk factors and the outcome of IRDS in Al-Khansa'a Maternity and Children hospital in Al Mosul.

Patients and methods: 106 neonates, 61 Males (58%) and 45 females (42%) were admitted to the neonatal care unit in Al Khansa'a Maternity and Children hospital during the period from the first of March 2000 to the 31 December 2000. with the clinical diagnosis of IRDS were observed

Results: Higher incidence occurred in neonates of 31-32 week gestational age and mainly in male. Mothers aged from 20-24 years old have the highest incidence of affected neonates. 40 (37.7%) mothers aged between 20-40 year. The main factor associated with premature labour was Antepartum hemorrhage (APH) which was present in 20 mothers (22%). Previous history of IRDS in the family was present in 9 cases (8.5%). Cesarean section was a significant risk factor for IRDS. The majority of neonates (74%) with IRDS have APGAR score more above 7 after 1 minutes. 28 neonates (26%) have APGAR score below 7 at 1 and 7 minutes and 5 ($X^2 = 8.281$, $P = < 0.004$) (highly significant). 69(65%) neonates survived, and 37 (34.9%) died. The main cause of death was Apnea and respiratory failure = (59%).

Introduction

Idiopathic respiratory distress syndrome (IRDS) occurs in 1-3% of all births. This incidence is inversely related to the gestational age and birth weight. It occurs in 60-80% of infants less than 28 weeks of

gestational age. IRDS is responsible for the deaths of many Preterm infants throughout the world each year. Surfactant deficiency (decreased production and secretion) is the primary cause of IRDS. The disease has a wide spectrum of severity from mild respiratory distress lasting 2 or 3 days to a rapidly fatal illness causing death within few hours. The natural course of classic IRDS is that of increasing severity during the first 24-48hr of life followed by a period of stability lasting another 48hr before improvement occurs. Early provision of intensive observation and care of high risk newborn infants can significantly reduce morbidity and mortality due to IRDS. [1, 2,3,4,5, 6]. The Aim of this study is to determine the incidence, sex distribution, associated risk factors and the outcome of IRDS in Al - Khansa'a Maternity and Children hospital.

Patient and method: 106 neonates, 61 Males (58%), and 45 females (42%) were admitted to the neonatal care unit (NCU) in Al-Khansa'a Maternity and Children hospital during the period from the first of March 2000 to December 31 2000 with the clinical diagnosis of IRDS were observed. The clinical diagnosis of IRDS was made by the presence of 2 of the following signs: Tachypnea (R.R. > 60 / min.), Expiratory grunting, Sternal and intercostal recession, Cyanosis in room air, supported by the radiological findings which include fine granular, ground glass appearance, and air bronchogram. In addition to full history and clinical examination, chest X ray was done to all of them. Brain ultrasound was done to 4 in to confirm intraventricular haemorrhage. Blood culture and other investigations were done on need according to specific condition and complications occurred. Babies with transient

tachypnea of the newborn (TTN) and meconium aspiration were excluded from this study. All patients were treated with O₂, intravenous fluid antibiotics from this study. All patients were treated with O₂, intravenous fluid antibiotics (on empiric basis) as ampicillin with gentamicin or with third generation cephalosporin. Apnea were fully resuscitated by suction, incubation, and aminophylline when necessary. Blood transfusion was given to two patients with pulmonary hemorrhage (PH). The number of live deliveries during the period of the study in Al Khansa'a maternity and children Hospital was 14360 with 106 (0.75 %) of them suffering from IRDS.

Results

Higher incidence occurred in neonates of 31-32 wk gestational age and mainly in male. Table (1). Mothers aged from 20-24 years old have the highest incidence of affected neonates 40 (37.7%) mothers aged between 20-40 years 32 mothers (30 %) aged between 25-29 years, 17 mothers (16 %) aged between 35-39. years, 7 mothers (6.6 %) were under 19 years, 6 mothers (5.6 %) aged between 30-34 years, and 4 mothers (3.7 %) were above 40 years. The main factor associated with premature labour was Antepartum hemorrhage (APH) which was present in 20 mothers (22 %). Previous history of IRDS in the family was present in 9 cases (8.5%). Table (2) shows factors associated with premature labour. Cesarean section was a significant risk factor for IRDS. Table (3) shows the type of delivery of the baby with the number of affected patients. The majority of patients (74%) affected with IRDS have APGAR score more above 7. after 1 and 5 minutes. 28 neonates (26%) have APGAR score below 7 at 1 and 5 minutes ($X^2 = 8.281$, $P = < 0.004$ (highly significant). 69(65%) neonates survived, and 37 (34.9%) died. The main cause of death was Apnea and respiratory failure (RF) = (59 %). Table (4). Shows the causes of death. Most of neonates (35 %) required supplemental oxygen for 4 days. 49 neonates were 7 days or less. Those who stayed for longer time, most of them

were suffering from septicemia or because of delay oral feeding.

Table 1: Show Sex distribution of the patient according their birth weight and gestational age

Groups of Birth weights and gestational age	Total No.	Male	Fem ale	M :F
1 ≤0.999 kg (≤28 wk).	11	7	4	1.7 : 1
2 1 – 1.499 kg (29-30 wk)	27	14	13	1.07: 1
3 1500 –1.699 kg (31-32 wk)	30	19	11	1.7 :1
4 1.700 – 1.999 kg (33-34 wk)	26	14	12	1.1 :1
5 2 –2.499 kg (35-36 wk)	9	5	4	1.2 :1
6 ≥2.500 kg (≥37 wk)	3	2	1	2 : 1
Total	106	61	45	1.3 : 1
		(58%)	(42 %)	1

Table 2: Factors which associated with premature labour

Risk Factor.	Number of Patients.
APH	20 (16 accidental and 4 placenta previa)
Multiple Pregnancy	14 (12 twins,1 triplet,1 Quadriplet)
Infections	10 (4 systemic,4 vaginal,2 congenital)
Cervical incompetence.	5
Pre eclampsia.	5
Polyhydramnios.	6
Fetal distress.	8
Premature rupture of membrane	6
Mothers with more than 5 children.	7
Teenage Pregnancy.	5

Discussion

The incidence of IRDS in Al Khansa'a Hospital during the period of study was 0.75 % among all live birth deliveries, similar incidence was reported by Scope J W [7] The gestational age of about 89 % of the babies was less than 34 weeks and birth weight was less than 1.990 kg; 58 % were males and 42 % were females, their these findings are consistent with the finding by other studies [7, 8] Associated risk factors for premature deliveries and IRDS were present in 86

.mothers Young maternal age is considered a risk factor in this study. 47 mothers (44 %) were under 24 years. A similar finding was reported by Edwards A D [4].Antepartum Hemorrhage in this study was present in 20 mothers (22 %). This finding differs from previous papers [9] considering APH a rare risk factor for prematurity. Chronic hypertension or pregnancy induced hypertension was present in 5 mothers (6 %), which is similar to the previous report of Carvalho MA [10] The incidence of IRDS was higher among babies who did not require resuscitation. at birth (74%) but mortality rate was higher in those babies who had low APGAR SCORE at delivery and who required immediate resuscitation at birth (57%). The mortality rate was 35% while it was 10-30 % in other studies Carlow [11,12],this difference is attributed to the use of antenatal steroid , postnatal surfactant and the improved mode of ventilation as CPAP.

Conclusion: The incidence of IRDS was 0.75 % among deliveries. The highest incidence was in neonates who were 31-32 wks of gestation with a birth weight of 1.500- 1.699 kg and with male predominance. The main risk factors for IRDS were Antepartum hemorrhage, history of previous IRDS in the family and Cesarean section delivery The mortality rate was 35% and the main cause of death was apnea and respiratory failure

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Table (3): Shows the type of delivery of the baby with the number of affected patient

Type of Delivery	No of deliveries	Total No of affected patients	No of deaths
N. V.	12265 (85 %)	81 (76 %)	28 (34 %)
C S	2095 (15 %)	25 (24 %)	9 (36 %)
Total	14360	106 (0.75 %)	37 (34.9 %)

$X^2 = 6.935$ $P = < 0.008$ (highly significant).

Table (3). Shows the causes of death.

Birth wt groups	No of Death	Causes of Death		
		Apnea &RF	Sepsis	IVH and /or PH
≤0.999 kg (≤28wk)	8 (72%)	4	2	2
1-1.499 kg (29-30wk)	11 (40%)	9	2	
1.5-1.699kg(31-32wk)	7 (23 %)	3	2	2
1.700-1.999 kg (33-34wk)	8 (30%)	4	1	3
2-2.499 kg (35-36wk)	2 (22%)	1	1	
2.500kg (≥37 wk)	1 (33%)	1		
Total	37(34.9%)	22 (59 %)	8(%)	7(19%)

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